

An Ideal TPS Relational Analysis

Jason J Bell, Gilberto García

NAVAIR Jacksonville, FL
6206 Aviation Avenue, Building 6206, Room H-3C
Jacksonville, FL 32221-8112

Phone: (904)-317-1691, Email: {jason.j.bell, gilberto.garcia1}@navy.mil

Abstract— *The collection and analysis of Test Program Set (TPS) historical data has been a need for developers looking to reduce call-out and cost; and improve diagnostics test times. This paper will discuss the ideal TPS and runtime data required in order to reduce development cost and speed End to End (ETE) runtime by having a simple TPS results historic database. This historic database that we introduce is an alternative to Smart TPS.*

Keywords – *TPS database, TPS development cost, TPS Test Results, data mining, maintenance actions, diagnostics, ATML.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Test program development and implementation spends a significant amount of its costs on minimizing ambiguity call-outs. As Unit Under Tests (UUTs) and internal components get more complicated and when signals interconnect and feedback between replaceable subassemblies; fault isolation becomes more difficult, therefore more expensive. A simple approach to improving the fault isolation (reducing life-cycle costs) would be to use a very simple self-learning algorithm that can append to the current test program call-outs without any alteration to the test program, with minimal impact to the operator and minor changes to the Test Executive (TE).

The automated collection of test results and the operator supplied list of the replaced components prior to each run of a TPS can be collected, indexed, distributed, and mined in real time to add useful information at the end of each failed TPS run. This information can be used to automatically improve Test Program results to reduce the repair actions necessary to bring faulty equipment back into Ready-For-Issue (RFI) condition. These improvements to the Test Programs require *no changes to the TPSs*. The programming changes to the Automatic Test Equipment (ATE) Test Executive (TE) are minor and easily implemented. The data collection and redistribution, absent any network connections to the ATE, can be included with existing methods of data collection of the ATE asset run time totalizer (RTT) data and distribution of software updates.

Further, the collected test results can be studied for many purposes including prognostics evaluation, suggested entry points, and repair/adjustment of test programs.

II. BACKGROUND

Test Programs are developed to detect and isolate faults. The ambiguity groups are commonly multiple replaceable components. The standard assumption is only one failure exists. In these cases, the other components in the ambiguity group are good and being replaced unnecessarily, sometimes at significant cost. The TPS programmer has ordered the ambiguity groups from most likely to least likely, but that order is usually based on simulated estimates that are often wrong. In addition, the actual fault is sometimes not in the ambiguity group, resulting in more extensive rework, manual diagnostics or disposal of the entire unit under test (UUT). To address this problem, Test Program operators often, by their own initiative, created gouge sheets for each part number UUT. These gouge sheets accumulated years of experience for commonly failed test results and the most successful repair actions for given failed test results. This tribal knowledge was isolated and easily lost. This proposal attempts to automate the collection and application of this “gouge” data.

III. REQUIREMENTS

The first requirement for this approach is that each and every test result is saved. At a minimum, the Automatic Test Equipment (ATE) test executive software should save every comparison performed including start time, TPS name, UUT part number, UUT serial number, station serial number, station configuration, current time, TPS start time, JCN number, operator ID, test number (includes main procedure statement number, current procedure name, current statement number), measured value, upper limit, lower limit, units and Go/ No Go status.

The second requirement is the ATE Test Executive (TE) should save every repair action including station serial number, current time, UUT part number, UUT serial number, and replaced assembly (pick list enforced from the existing TPS cross reference file).

This is enough information to determine the success or failure of any replaced item and the failed test that resulted. All collected test results would need to be combined via the easiest collection method (network, CD-ROM,...) to a single database. This database would need to then be made available to each ATE with replication and updates.

FIG. 1. OPERATOR AND TEST EXECUTIVE REQUIREMENT

The third requirement is for the test executive to append to the end of each TPS ambiguity call-outs, an ordered list of the likely cause of failure based on previously collected data. This list would have the most common successful repair action for this test failure and a probability of that action as successful repair. Then it would list the next most likely failure until all successful unique component repair actions for that test have been listed.

The fourth requirement is to display, immediately prior to the start of the TPS, a list of the most common first failed test numbers for the current TPS. This will give the operator the option of jumping into the entry point most likely to find the failure.

A. INPUTS

The test executives on the Navy's CASS family of testers are already able to collect data for every single test. This data includes the measured value, upper and lower limits, test numbers, times, operator, station and UUT serial numbers. This data can be continuously appended to a test results file during test program execution with minimal impact on ATE performance. This automated data will be stored in two tables Test_Results and TPS_Runs as defined in the data model later in this paper.

Additionally, the test program operator will need to answer one additional question prior to each run. The question of "What was your last repair action prior to this run?" can be answered by choosing components from a pick list built from the IMUTF_CROSS_REF.DAT or the .UUT file (or any file that lists all the replaceable assemblies). An additional option of "First Run" and "No repair action performed" and a line for user defined components should also be included in the pick

list. The input validation of using a pick list will help aggregate failure results by component name. This data will be stored in the Repair_Actions table as defined in the data model later in this paper.

B. OUTPUTS

Immediately prior to the test executive starting the TPS execution, the test executive will display a sorted list of the most common failed end-to-end tests for the current test program, with a count of failures for each test. (see Figure 3)

Upon the FINISH or TERMINATE of a TPS, the test executive will derive and display a list of historical parts replaced on this given Failed Test# with the number of times it actually fixed the UUT. As shown in figure 2, information sent to the operator's screen includes:

- Replaceable Part Number
- Ref Des
- Number of times replacement fixed problem
- Number of times replaced
- Percentage based on: "Number of times replacement fixed problem" / sum of all "Number of Times Replaced"

C. ACTIONS

The changes to the Test Executive can be summarized into actions that need to be performed before, during and after the execution of a TPS.

Pre TPS

- Ask User Last Repair Action
 - o pick list enforced
- Write Repair_Actions database record
- Write TPS_Runs database record
- Display most common failed tests for TPS

On-Test / Compare Trigger

- Write Test_Results Database record

Post TPS

- Look up in database by "Failed Test#"
- Accumulate summary info, sort by "Number of times replacement fixed problem"
- Display in TestExec output window

IV. DATA MODEL

The data collected can be stored into three relational database tables. A fourth table (TPS_Stats) may be created during database compilation by the ATE's datacenter. This fourth table is generated to expedite data analysis. TPS_Stats contains the number of End-To-End tests for each TPS and is derived from all available TPS Run data. The tables are as defined below.

Test Results

Station_Name	A40
UUT_Part#	A40
UUT_Serial#	A40
Current_Time	DateTime
TPS_Start_Time	DateTime
Operator_Name	A40
Measured_Value	A40
Upper_Limit	A40
Lower_Limit	A40
Units	A40
Test.MainLineLineNo	I6 *
Test.ProcedureName	A40 *
Test.ProcedureLineNo	I6 *

The three Test fields are abbreviated throughout this paper as Test. They are used as a unique pointer to each compare/test statement.

Repair Actions

Station_Name	A40
UUT_Part#	A40
UUT_Serial#	A40
Current_Time	DateTime **
Operator_Name	A40
ReplacedPart.RefDes	A40
ReplacedPart.Part#	A40
ReplacedPart.Cage	A5
ReplacedPart.Qty	Number
TPS_Start_Time	DateTime ***
Success_Level	A1 ***
Previous_FailedTest#.*	I6/A40/I6 ***

** (link to table TPS_Runs column TPS_Start_Time)

*** (algorithmically determined when data compiled)

TPS Runs

Station_Name	A40
UUT_Part#	A40
UUT_Serial#	A40
TPS_Start_Time	DateTime **
Operator_Name	A40

** (link to table Repair_Actions column TPS_Start_Time)

All tables are linked by multi-column index of (TPS_Start_Time, Station_Name).

Entity Relationship is many-to-one:

For each TPS_Runs there are 0 or more Test_Results.

For each TPS_Runs there are 0 or more Repair_Actions

For each Test_Results there are 0 or more Repair_Actions

TPS Stats

UUT_Part#	A30
maxETE_Test_Count	Number

V. REQUIRED CHANGES

The following is a list of changes to the operator:

1. At the beginning of a TPS run – complete the checklist page of replaceable components as example shown in figure 2.

FIG. 2. MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

2. Then display a list of the most common test number failures for the current TPS (notional example in Figure 3).

Prior Run Results for 4981950-3		
Test#	# of Failures	% of Failures
2700	8	40%
1040	5	25%
0710	4	20%
2105	2	10%
2750	1	5%

20		
Entry Point Menu		
1	050000	ETE
2	100000	Synchros
3	200000	Digital Tests
4	250000	Camera Tests
5	999900	Terminate TPS

FIG. 3. ENTRY POINT HINTS

3. At the end of a TPS run – read summary of most successful repair actions for similar failures, as shown in figure 4.

Most Successful Repair Actions for Test 273085: CompareResults:924060				
RefDes	Part Number	Replaced	Successful	% Success
1. A1	6123452-1	12	8	42%
2. A4	5289922-2	6	3	15%
3. A2	5123452-1	1	1	5%

FIG. 4. MOST SUCCESSFUL REPAIR ACTIONS FOR FAILED TEST

The following are changes to the ATE TE Runtime:

1. Save every test result into “Test_Results” database including all data described in Inputs section.
2. At TE launch of TPS, ask operator for previous repair action, store answer in “Repair_Actions” database.
3. At TE launch of TPS, display to operator, list of most common failed tests for current TPS.
4. Save every TPS run start into “TPS_Runs” database including all data described in Inputs section.
5. Modify routine that migrates RTT data to also include all 3 results database tables.
6. Modify any routine that pushes new disks to ATE to include compiled sum of all collected and compiled “results” database tables..
7. At TPS Finish or Terminate, use this runs first failed test to search database and give list of successful repair actions for this failed test.

The following needs to be built to run at the data collection point:

1. Combine all incoming data from each site into single database.
2. Create routine to compile all Test_Results, TPS_Runs, and Repair_Actions into form to redistribute to all ATE in field. (see algorithms for database compilation, later in this paper)

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

To test these changes and minimize operator confusion it should be implemented in 3 phases.

- Phase 1** Save All Test Results
 Save All Run Starts
 Ask operator for replaced parts
 Return results with RTT data

During phase 1 test results and TPS starts data is collected on each ATE and bundled with other existing data transfers from the operational sites back to the ATE’s central software support activity. If no other actions recommended in this paper are implemented, this one action can stand on its own in supplying useful data to TPS support teams and TPS migration teams and future ATE upgrade teams.

- Phase 2.** Build database compiler
 Build database search for all repair actions for given failed test
 Build Operator interface and data save for Last Repair Actions
 Test

This phase is the testing and debugging phase. Real data will allow these concepts described in this paper to be tested. Simulated runs targeting specific failure points should generate new Post TPS “Successful Repair Action” summaries that can be validated against expected results.

This is the phase where problems may cause phase 1 to be re-implemented with changes to the Test Exec data collection routines. One likely problem is the non-specificity of test numbers due to actual tests being in the middle of a chain of procedure calls between the main-line code and the actual COMPARE statement. This may require the entire procedure call stack and calling statement numbers to be included in the “Failed Test#” column of the Test_Results table.

- Phase 3.** Distribute compiled database to all ATE
 Display most common failed test#s at start of TPS
 Display most successful repair actions at end of TPS

This phase is the implementation phase. Rolling out the remaining Test Executive change whereby “most common failed test numbers” and “successful Repair Actions” summary is displayed to the operator using the distributed compiled test results database.

Phase 4. Future Improvements

This phase takes ideas for improvement and tests them then implements the successful ones. The growing database collect will allow testing of hypotheses on real-world data.

- Some ideas for future improvements include:
) Generating warnings to the TPS maintainers when certain tests are always close to the upper or lower limit
) Prognostics based on UUT serial numbers and their test results creeping out of tolerance compared to later actual failures on the same serial number UUTs.
) Altering the “Successful Repair Actions” displayed to consider failure above the upper limit, vs. below the lower limit, or near failures to way out failures, or timeout failures.

Notional Algorithms to be Implemented

The following SQL and pseudo-code are intended to further define the concepts described. These have not been debugged in any way.

Algorithms For Database Compilation

Add all available uploaded database tables to make 3 big tables. Simple append to each table is sufficient.

Find out # of tests for an ETE for each part#

```
--*** Basic theory is to look at all runs for TPS
--*** Include only runs with no failures
--*** Find maximum count of distinct test numbers
--*** Outer loop of all no-fail TPS runs
Select Station_Name,TPS_Start_Time,UUT_Part#
  from TPS_Runs r
 where 0=(select count(*) from Test_Results tr
         where tr.TPS_Start_Time=r.TPS_Start_Time
         and tr.Station_Name=r.Station_Name
         and tr.measured_value
         between(tr.lower_limit,tr.upper_limit))
```

```
--*** Inner loop for each no-fail TPS run
--*** Find maximum count of distinct test numbers
  a. Select count(distinct Test#.*)) from
      Test_Results tr2 where
      tr2.TPS_Start_Time=r.TPS_Start_Time
      and tr2.Station_Name=r.Station_Name
  b. Select maxETE_Test_Count from
      TPS_Stats where
      UUT_Part#=r.UUT_Part#
  c. If( count > maxETE_Test_Count) then
      Update TPS_Stats
```

For every Repair Action determine original TPS Run Time

```
--*** Find the closest run-time prior to the repair action time
Update Repair_Actions ra
  set TPS_Start_Time= ra.Current_Time+
  (Select min(ra.Current_Time -
              TPS_Start_Time) dt
   where TPS_Start_Time < ra.Current_Time
   and UUT_Part#=ra.UUT_Part#)
 where TPS_Start_Time is null
```

For every Repair Action determine if it was successful

```
--*** tr_NoGo is count of failing tests for given TPS_Runs
Select count(distinct Test#.*) tr_NoGo
  from test_results
 where TPS_Start_Time=ra.TPS_Start_Time
       and measured_value between (lower_limit,upper_limit)
```

```
--*** tr_NoGo is count of failing tests for given TPS_Runs
Select count(distinct Test#.*) tr_NoGo
  from test_results
 where where TPS_Start_Time=ra.TPS_Start_Time
       and measured_value between (lower_limit,upper_limit)
```

```
Select maxETE_Test_count cntETE
  from TPS_Stats
 where UUT_Part#=ra.UUT_Part#
```

```
--*** If count of distinct passing tests >= ETE count
--*** then success is positive count of ETE tests
--*** Else if count distinct of passing tests >= ETE
--*** but there were some failures (eg Pass on Repeat)
--*** success set to negative number of Nogos
--*** Else success is 0 for failed to complete ETE
if(tr_NoGo>=cntETE and tr_NOGO=0) then
  update success_level=tr_NoGo
else if(tr_NoGo>=cntETE and tr_NOGO>0) then
  update success_level=0-tr_NoGo
else success_level=0
```

For each Repair Action ra where ra.Previous_FailedTest#.* is null determine last Failed Test# (do not count if repeat/passed)

```
--*** Find time of first failed test in a given run
Select min(Current_Time) minCT
  from test_results tr
 where measured_value not between (lower_limit,upper_limit)
       and TPS_Start_Time=ra.TPS_Start_Time
       and 0=(select count(*) from test_results tr2
              where tr2.TPS_Start_Time=ra.TPS_Start_Time
              and tr2.measured_value
              between(tr2.lower_limit,tr2.upper_limit) and
              tr2.Test#.*=tr.Test#.*)
```

```
--*** Save the Test# as the Previous_Failed_Test# to link
--*** Repair_Actions to first failed test of previous run
Update Repair_Actions ra2 set ra2.Previous_Failed_Test#.* =
  (select Test#.*
   from test_results
   where current_time=minCT
   and
   TPS_Run_Time=ra.TPS_Run_Time)
 where ra2.TPS_Run_Time=ra.TPS_Run_Time
```

Algorithm for Run Time “Most Successful Repair Actions”
These algorithms run on the ATE at the end of a failed TPS run. To improve runtime, the fields TPS_Start_Time and FaileTest#.* should be indexed.

Find Current TPS Run’s First Failed Test#.* (where it did not pass on repeat)

```
--*** thisTPS.TPS_Start_Time refers to the Test Exec
--*** holding the start time of the current TPS so we
--*** can find information in the database for this current
--*** TPS run
```

```
Select min(Current_Time) minCTFirstFailed
  from test_results tr
where measured_value not between (lower_limit,upper_limit)
  and TPS_Start_Time=thisTPS.TPS_Start_Time
  and 0=(select count(*)
  from test_results tr2
  where tr2.TPS_Start_Time=ra.TPS_Start_Time
  and tr2.measured_value
  between(tr2.lower_limit,tr2.upper_limit)
  and tr2.Test#.*=tr.Test#.*)
```

```
select Test#.*
  into thisTPS.FirstFailedTest#.*
  from test_results
  where current_time= minCTFirstFailed
  and TPS_Start_Time=thisTPS.TPS_Start_Time)
```

Select Descending list of most successful Repair Actions for given Failed Test#.*

```
Select ReplacedPart.RefDes, ReplacedPart.Part#,
  sum(ReplacedPart.qty) SumQty
  from Repair_Actions ra
where Previous_FailedTest#.* = thisTPS.FirstFailedTest#.*
  and success_level <> 0
  group by ReplacedPart.RefDes, ReplacedPart.Part#
  order by SumQty
```

Include in each row retrieved above the number of times part has been replaced

```
--*** For each row returned by the previous SQL cursor
Select sum(ReplacedPart.qty)
  from repair_actions ra2
where ra2.uut_part# = ra.uut_part#
  and ra2.Previous_FailedTest#.*=thisTPS.FirstFailedTest#.*
```

VII. PRIVACY

For unclassified testing; the ATE, TPS and RTT information is just a record of test results and asset health status exported to optical media and/or transferred to local network, then imported into the Enterprise node for analysis and data collection. For classified testing; network connection is removed from the station and no information is exported to optical media. At this point in time there is no general solution for classified TPSs. When classified TPSs follow the rule of normalizing their results to be centered around 0 or 1, then the results would be unclassified and usable for these purposes.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper described the implementation of an ideal TPS runtime data requirement in which the automatically generated and collected data gets exported to removable media and processed offline by an Enterprise server. The compilation of data from all ATE at all sites is returned to each ATE. The ATE uses this data to suggest to the operator the best entry point for failure detection. Additionally, the ATE augments the TPS call-outs with an ever growing, ever improving, ever more accurate list of the most successful repair actions for whatever test failures occur. Automatically improving the most important TPS tests, since whatever tests fail the most often will get the most statistically significant improvements in accuracy of the replaceable assembly. These improvements will save time and money at a low cost and low risk while not touching the huge investment in Test Program Sets.